

Solute-Solvent Interaction of Phenylalanine in various Organic Solvents

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Free energies of interaction of phenylalanine for transfer from water to the organic solvents ethanol, dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide methanol, acetonitrile dioxane and acetone are calculated from solubility measurements at 25°. Some microscopic interactions of phenylalanine in the organic solvents under consideration are also calculated and their values discussed.

THE literature reveals many works on solute-solvent interaction of weak acids in non-aqueous solvents^{1,2}.

The solute-solvent interaction of some amino acids in mixtures of both formic acid-ethyl methyl ketone and acetic acid-ethyl methyl ketone have been studied³.

Experimental

The organic solvents EtOH, DMF, DMSO, MeOH, acetonitrile (AN), dioxane (Di) and acetone (Ac) were of B.D.H. chemicals. The saturated solution of phenylalanine (Riedel) was prepared in the organic solvents. The solubility of phenylalanine in each solvent was determined gravimetrically³. The densities were measured by using a Hereaus-Paar DMA-50 densimeter.

Results and Discussion

The solubilities of phenylalanine in water and some organic solvents were measured (Table 1). From the molal solubilities (*S*), the interaction free energies of transfer of phenylalanine from water to the organic solvents are calculated by using equation (1).

$$\Delta_w^*G^\circ = -2.303 RT [\log S_s - \log S_w] \quad (1)$$

where *S* is the solubility in molal scale of phenylalanine in the organic solvents (*s*) and water (*w*), respectively. The calculated free energy values for transfer of phenylalanine from water to the organic solvents following equation (1) are presented in Table 1.

The Van der Waals volume of phenylalanine was calculated by applying Bondi model⁴ taking into consideration the overlapping volumes between the atoms in phenylalanine molecule. The overlapping volume between any covalent two atoms can be calculated by applying equations (2) and (3) on knowing the radii of each atom (*r*₁ and *r*₂)⁴ and the distance between their centers (*l*). The calculated overlapping volume (ΔV_{2-1}) were estimated for each covalent bond in phenylalanine molecule (Table 2).

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY (*S*), SOLUBILITY PRODUCT (pK_{sp}) AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER ($\Delta_w^*G^\circ$) OF PHENYLALANINE FROM WATER TO VARIOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 25°

Solvent	$\frac{S}{M}$	pK_{sp}^*	$\Delta_w^*G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹
H ₂ O	0.154 0	0.812 5	0
EtOH	$3.971 0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.401 1	9.100 5
DMF	$4.822 0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.316 7	8.584 6
DMSO	$6.508 0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.186 5	7.841 5
MeOH	0.029 5	1.530 2	4.095 8
AN	$9.080 5 \times 10^{-3}$	4.041 8	18.429 7
Di	$1.059 4 \times 10^{-3}$	2.974 9	12.340 9
Ac	$1.846 4 \times 10^{-3}$	2.733 7	10.964 2

* $pK_{sp} = -\log S$.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF COVALENT BONDS IN PHENYLALANINE MOLECULE

Bond	r_1^* Å	r_2 Å	<i>l</i> Å	ΔV_{2-1} cm ³ mol ⁻¹
C—C ^a	1.70	1.70	0.61	7.546
C—H	1.20	1.70	1.00	1.092
N—H	1.20	1.55	1.55	0.946
O—H	1.20	1.52	1.46	1.030
C—O ^a	1.52	1.70	1.50	2.608
C—N	1.55	1.70	1.60	2.551

**r*₁ in any covalent bond is taken as the small atom in each bond.

^aMean value for both single and double bonds.

$$m = r_2^2 - r_1^2 + l^2/2l, \quad h_1 = r_1 + l - m, \quad h_2 = r_2 - m \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta V_{2-1} = \pi h_2^2 (r_2 - h_2/3) \quad (3)$$

The terms in equations (2) and (3) can be explained as follows,

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Summing all the Van der Waals volumes (V_w) for all atoms in phenylalanine molecule and subtracting all the overlapping volumes from it gives the exact Van der Waals volume for phenylalanine ($222.648 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

The dipole-dipole free energies of interactions of phenylalanine with the organic solvents were calculated by applying equation (4)⁵.

$$\Delta G_{\text{dip-dip}}^{\circ} = -8/9 N \pi d_o \frac{\mu_1^2 \mu_2^2}{k T \sigma_1^3} \quad (4)$$

where d_o is the density of pure solvents, μ_1 the dipole moment of solute, μ_2 the dipole moment of the organic solvent and σ_1 that of the solvated. The used dipole moments for the organic solvents and phenylalanine ($\mu_1 = 2.10$) were taken from literature⁶. The estimated dipole free energies for phenylalanine are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF THE ORGANIC SOLVENTS OF INTERACTION OF PHENYLALANINE IN PURE ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 25°

Solvent	σ SPT* Å	μ_2	σ_1 Å	$\Delta G_{\text{dip-dip}}^{\circ}$ $\times 10^{-6}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
H ₂ O	2.770	1.86	6.529	-16.188
EtOH	4.350	1.68	8.109	-27.117
DMF	4.930	3.86	8.689	-31.280
DMSO	4.910	3.90	8.669	-5.433
MeOH	3.700	3.70	7.459	-13.344
AN	4.160	3.92	7.919	-7.269
Di	5.164	0.45	8.921	-32.386
Ac	4.770	2.88	8.529	-0.036

*Ref. 6.

The partial molar volume of phenylalanine (V°) in the organic solvents was calculated by dividing its molecular weight by the density of the saturated solutions (d). The solvated Van der Waals volumes of phenylalanine (V_{sw}) can be calculated by using the constant value of packing density (P) for big molecules as in equation (5)⁷.

$$P = \frac{V_{sw}}{V^{\circ}} = 0.661 \pm 0.017 \quad (5)$$

The electrostriction volume (V_e) defined as the volume of the solute compressed by the solvent in

the solvation processes was calculated by using equation (6)^{7,8}.

$$V_e = V_w - V^{\circ} \quad (6)$$

V° , V_{sw} and V_e values thus calculated for phenylalanine in the organic solvents under consideration are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DENSITY OF SATURATED SOLUTIONS (d), MOLAR VOLUME (V°), SOLVATED VAN DER WAALS VOLUME (V_{sw}) AND ELECTROSTRICTION VOLUME (V_e) OF PHENYLALANINE IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 25°

Solvent	d g cm ⁻³	V° cm ³ mol ⁻¹	V_{sw} cm ³ mol ⁻¹	V_e cm ³ mol ⁻¹
H ₂ O	1.024 63	161.219	106.566	61.429
EtOH	0.825 54	200.099	132.265	22.549
DMF	0.952 92	173.350	114.584	49.298
DMSO	1.113 61	148.337	98.051	74.311
MeOH	0.816 69	202.267	133.698	20.381
AN	0.778 52	212.185	140.254	10.463
Di	1.029 62	160.438	106.049	62.210
Ac	0.800 81	206.278	136.349	16.370

It is concluded that the increase in the free energy of transfer values for phenylalanine in the organic solvents was accompanied by the increase in dipole-dipole interaction free energies, partial molar volume and solvated Van der Waals volume due to the increase in solute-solvent interactions.

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